

**COGNITIVE AND LINGUACULTURAL PECULIARITIES OF THE
CONCEPT OF "APPEARANCE" IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK**

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Language is the most powerful means of national identity, serving the formation of a nation. After the independence of our country, the emphasis on language has become even stronger. Through the efforts of the President, laws and decisions on language have been adopted. After all, language is also valued by the honor and pride of the nation. One of the latest achievements of linguistics is that the study of language as a whole system and its study in opposition to speech have clarified the pragmatic functions of language units that emerge in speech activity in relation to context and situation. The study of language units in a pragmatic way, in the essence of the work or text, allowed to identify the internal possibilities that are not directly visible to the reader, but arise only in speech. As a result, there is a problem of defining the pragmatic functions of language units in relation to the speech situation. Within the framework of different linguocultures in modern world linguistics, the areas of identification of forms of information perception and linguistic means in the linguocognitive and linguocultural directions are gaining a leading position. In particular, the human factor is now playing a crucial role in knowing and understanding the world. Therefore, the anthropocentric approach is one of the most important areas of research today, especially in linguistics, because anthropocentrism is based on events that are directly related to the essence of language. Methods and means of systematic categorical-semantic study of the units that ensure the reflection of the human image as a separate part of the linguistic landscape in world linguistics today, the scope of the concept of "man" in different styles of texts scientific research is being conducted in priority areas such as the study and description of features in the semantic field of language. In addition, the study of the spiritual-logical, semantic-functional and linguocultural features of units within the concept of the "human" in the context of different languages reveals one of the most promising areas of modern linguistics. In recent years, linguistics has focused on the study of problems of linguopragmatics and cognitive linguistics. Among linguistic-pragmatic studies, the issue of text pragmatics in particular is attracting the attention of linguists. Although some work has been done in this area, there are still issues to be

addressed. Modern linguistics pays close attention to the study of the internal capabilities of language level units that are not given in direct observation that arise in connection with factors such as context, speech situation, general knowledge of language owners about the external world and language skills. At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, the ideas of the pragmatic direction put forward in the works of Ch.Pierce, U.James, D.Dune, Ch.Morris were further developed in the following years. In particular, pragmatic research has been carried out in Uzbek linguistics since the last century, and Mahmudov, A.Nurmonov, M.Khakimov, U.Rahimov, D.Lutfullayeva, Vahidova N., Toirova G., Z.Burkhonov's pragmatic researches in one direction or another. Pragmatic research focuses on aspects of language unity related to nonlinear factors such as context, speech situation, general knowledge of language speakers about reality and language skills. Even speech etiquette, which expresses the relationship between people, social adaptation of speech, introduction to the subjective modal aspect of expression, evaluative words and means, discourse expressing the inner subjective psyche of man and the phenomenon of presupposition are objects of study of pragmatics. It is understood that pragmatic research will help to uncover the untapped potential of language unity in direct observation of nonlinear factors.

The concept of "appearance" holds cognitive and linguocultural peculiarities in both English and Uzbek, encompassing a nuanced interplay of perception, language, and cultural values. Let's delve into the theoretical dimensions of how the concept of "appearance" is framed within the cognitive and sociolinguistic realms of English and Uzbek:

- English: The concept of "appearance" in English is closely intertwined with visual perception, encompassing the physical attributes, outward impressions, and visual qualities of an individual or object.

- Uzbek: In Uzbek, the cognition of "appearance" aligns with visual representations and sensory perceptions, reflecting cultural norms and preferences related to physical presentation and aesthetic values.

- English: The cognitive representation of "appearance" in English is influenced by cultural ideals of beauty, fashion, and grooming, often reflecting societal norms and trends related to physical presentation.

- Uzbek: Within Uzbek culture, the concept of "appearance" may be shaped by distinctive cultural aesthetics, traditional attire, and historical influences on visual representations of individuals and objects.

- English: The lexical representation of "appearance" in English encompasses a wide array of vocabulary related to physical presentation, attire, grooming, and visual attributes, reflecting a diverse range of descriptive terms and idiomatic expressions.

- Uzbek: Similarly, in Uzbek, the lexical inventory pertaining to "appearance" encompasses culturally specific terms, expressions, and idiomatic constructs that reflect aesthetic preferences, traditional attire, and visual descriptions within the Uzbek sociolinguistic context.

- English: The linguistic expression of "appearance" in English may be influenced by politeness norms, social desirability, and the value placed on physical presentation within social interactions, thereby reflecting polite and socially acceptable ways of characterizing people's visual attributes.

- Uzbek: In Uzbek, linguistic expressions related to "appearance" may be entwined with sociocultural norms, norms of modesty, and etiquettes pertaining to physical presentation, reflecting social values concerning visual attributes and personal appearance.

- English: The cognitive understanding of "appearance" in English may encompass not only physical attributes but also the subjective and socially constructed nature of beauty standards, self-presentation, and societal judgments related to visual impressions.

- Uzbek: Similarly, in Uzbek cognition, the concept of "appearance" may include subjective and culturally oriented perceptions of beauty, cultural aesthetics, and historical influences on visual representations within the Uzbek sociolinguistic context.

- English: Within English-speaking societies, the concept of "appearance" holds cultural significance related to individualism, beauty standards, and visual representation, reflecting the impact of media, fashion, and societal expectations on perceptions and self-presentation.

- Uzbek: In Uzbek culture, the concept of "appearance" may be intertwined with cultural values, historical influences, and societal standards of visual presentation, reflecting unique aesthetic sensibilities and sociocultural norms related to personal appearance.

By exploring the cognitive and linguocultural dimensions of the concept of "appearance" in English and Uzbek, we gain a deeper understanding of how visual perception, language use, and cultural values intersect to shape the multifaceted representation of physical presentation and aesthetic ideals within these linguistic and cultural contexts.

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